

Key to European Species of the Genus *Oxyna* Robineau-Desvoidy, 1830 (Diptera: Tephritidae), with New Records from Russia

V. A. Korneyev

I.I.Schmalhausen Institute of Zoology
National Academy of Sciences of Ukraine
Bogdan Chmielnicki St. 15
01601 Kiev, Ukraine

E-mail: valery.korneyev@gmail.com

D. A. Evstigneev

Civil Aviation High School of Ulyanovsk,
Mozhaysky St. 8/8,
432071, Ulyanovsk, Russia

E-mail: temporaria@yandex.ru

Korneyev V. A. & Evstigneev D. A. Key to European Species of the Genus *Oxyna* Robineau-Desvoidy, 1830 (Diptera: Tephritidae), with New Records from Russia. Summary. An interactive pictorial key to species of the genus *Oxyna* is provided. New material from European Russia (Volga basin) is listed, including some previously poorly known species. *Oxyna variabilis* Chen, 1938 is recorded from Europe for the first time. Morphological characters of all the species are illustrated.

Key words: Diptera, Tephritidae, *Oxyna*, Palaearctic Region, Europe, key, distribution.

Корнеев В. А. и Евстигнеев Д. А. Ключи для определения видов рода *Oxyna* Robineau-Desvoidy, 1830 (Diptera: Tephritidae) с новыми находками из России и Украины. Резюме. Приведен интерактивный иллюстрированный ключ для определения видов рода *Oxyna*. Приведен новый материал из Европейской России (бассейн Волги), включая несколько мало известных до настоящего времени видов. *Oxyna variabilis* Chen, 1938 отмечена впервые из Европы. Приведены иллюстрации морфологических признаков всех рассмотренных видов.

Ключевые слова: Diptera, Tephritidae, *Oxyna*, Палеарктика, Европа, таблица для определения, распространение.

Корнєєв В. О. і Євстигнєєв Д. О. Ключі для визначення видів роду *Oxyna* Robineau-Desvoidy, 1830 (Diptera: Tephritidae) з новими знахідками з Росії. Резюме. Наведено інтерактивний ілюстрований ключ для визначення видів роду *Oxyna*. Наведено новий матеріал з Європейської Росії (басейн Волги), включаючи кілька маловідомих донині видів. *Oxyna variabilis* Chen, 1938 відзначено вперше з Європи. Наведено ілюстрації морфологічних ознак всіх розглянутих видів.

Ключевые слова: Diptera, Tephritidae, *Oxyna*, Палеарктика, Європа, ключ для визначення, поширення.

Introduction

The genus *Oxyna* belongs in the *Campiglossa* group of genera of the tribe Tephritini (Korneyev, 1999). Most *Oxyna* can be easily recognized from the combination of one frontal, two orbital, and short and white lateral vertical setae, with wide and bare frons, bare vein R_{4+5} and reticulate wing pattern with numerous yellowish or brownish dots along with larger hyaline spots, including 3 of them in cell r1, with male phallus having very densely setulose preglans (similarly to other genera of *Campiglossa*

group, but much stronger expressed) and glans with simple tubular acrophallus (modified into so-called “rostrum” in the other genera of *Campiglossa* group).

With three Nearctic (*O. aterrima* (Doane 1899), *O. palpalis* (Coquillett, 1904), and *O. utahensis* Quisenberry, 1949) and 23 nominal Palaearctic species (*O. albipila* Loew, 1869; *O. albofasciata* Chen, 1938; *O. amurensis* Hendel, 1927; *O. distincta* Chen, 1938; *O. dracunculina* Richter, 1990; *O. fasciata* Wang, 1996; *O. flavipennis* (Loew, 1844); *O. fusca* Chen, 1938; *O. gansuica* Wang, 1998; *O. guttatofasciata* (Loew, 1850); *O. longicauda* Korneyev,

1990; *O. lutulenta* Loew, 1869; *O. menyuanica* Wang, 1998; *O. nasuta* Hering, 1936; *O. nebulosa* (Wiedemann, 1817); *O. obesa* Loew, 1862; *O. parietina* (Linnaeus, 1758); *O. parva* Chen, 1938; *O. stackelbergi* Korneyev, 1990; *O. superflava* Freidberg, 1974; *O. tarbagatajensis* Korneyev, 1990; *O. tianshanica* Korneyev, 1990; *O. variabilis* Chen, 1938) (see Korneyev, 2004 for further details), some of them with high probability are conspecific to other known species, but no new synonymies are considered here.

Asian species have been recently keyed by Freidberg & Kugler (1989), Korneyev (1990); Wang (1998), and Korneyev & Ovchinnikova (2004). European species were keyed by Hendel (1927), Richter (1970), and Merz (1994). White (1988), Korneyev (1990), and Merz (1994) used the shape of female aculeus as an important diagnostic character, along with chaetotaxy and wing pattern; at the same time, male genitalia were found to be uniform throughout the whole genus.

Biology of *Oxya* remains poorly studied. Known larvae either form the rhizome bud galls on perennial grasses (*O. flavipennis* Loew and *O. nebulosa* Wiedemann) or feed in young shoots of perennial grasses and shrubs without forming galls (*O. albipila* Loew, *O. parietina* Linnaeus, *O. stackelbergi* Korneyev, possibly also *O. obesa* Loew). The species of *Oxya* are either captured in association with or reared from the plants of the tribe Anthemideae (*Achillea*, *Anthemis* and *Artemisia*).

Recent collecting of the fruit flies in European Russia, first of all, in steppes of Volga and Ural basins conducted by DAE, revealed some *Oxya* species, previously considered restricted to Central Asia. Based on this material, as well on study of a previously poorly known Iberian species *O. obesa*, a pictorial key to species known to occur in Europe (in its widest sense, eastwards to the Ural Mountains and Ural River) is provided.

Material and Methods

Acronyms for the institutions where specimens are deposited are:

CDE Dmitry Evstigneev private collection, Ulyanovsk;

SIZK I.I.Schmalhausen Institute of Zoology, National Academy of Sciences of Ukraine, Kiev, Ukraine;

ZMHB Museum für Naturkunde, Leibniz-Institut für Evolutions- und Biodiversitätsforschung an der Humboldt-Universität zu Berlin, Germany.

Labels of specimens written in the Cyrillic alphabet are translated or transliterated.

Oxya Robineau-Desvoidy, 1830

Type species: *Oxya flavescens* Robineau-Desvoidy (by subsequent designation of Hendel 1914: 96) (= *flavipennis* Loew).

Sinoxyna Chen, 1938: 84.

Type species: *Sinoxyna notabilis* Chen (OD) = *variabilis* Chen.

Grandoxyna Dirlbek & Dirlbek, 1971.

Type-species: *Grandoxyna gilva* Dirlbek & Dirlbek, 1971 (by original designation).

Diagnosis. Medium-sized (4.0–6.5 mm), rarely moderately small (3–4 mm) flies with densely microtrichose body, widely brown wing with a pattern of diffuse of small hyaline or yellowish dots and larger hyaline spots often confluent and forming hyaline crossbands, head with one (in some aberrant specimens two to three) frontal and two orbital setae, short and white lateral vertical seta and mixed black and white postocular setae, cell *bcu* (=cup) with moderately short lobe, vein R_{4+5} normally bare dorsally and ventrally (in some aberrant specimens with setulae dorsally or ventrally), phallus preglans with bunches of long spinulae and glans with short tubular acrophallus inside, female eversible membrane short spinulose, oviscape with or without preapical shoulders and steps; two pear-like spermathecae. Larvae in shoots of various asteraceous plants of the tribe Anthemideae (*Artemisia*, *Achillea*, *Leucanthemum* and related genera), with or without inducing galls.

Key to European species of *Oxya*

It is intended to be used as an authomathised interactive pictorial key. Each page contains two pictures (a red one, the couplet **a** and purple, anticouplet **b**). Read explanation of the characters and compare the characters in your specimen and on the picture. Then click the picture, which coincides with the characters of your specimen.

If your pdf reader supports the hyperlink options of this document, you will be automatically transferred to the next pair or couplet / anticouplet.

If it does not automatically transfer you, follow to the couplet with the number given in the right lower corner of the picture.

When you finally come up to a named species, click its picture to be transferred to the plate with all the important morphological details and a map of known distribution.

A list of new examined material, known distribution, and references are given after the pictorial key, in the end of this paper.

1a

Mesonotum with presutural dorsocentral seta.

Среднеспинка с предпшової дорсоцентральної щетинки (prst dc).

2

1b

Mesonotum without presutural dorsocentral seta.

Среднеспинка без предпшової дорсоцентральної щетинки.

3

2b

O. variabilis Chen

Aculeus evenly tapered, without shoulders; its apex without steps. Wing ochreous brown, with numerous partly confluent hyaline and yellow spots, less dimorphic, usually more extensively yellow dotted in male. —Вершинний членник яйцеклада рівномірно сужен, без верхішніх уступів. Крыло охряно-желтє, с более многочисленными желтыми точками у самца.

2a

O. flavipennis Loew

Aculeus conspicuously constricted, with blunt shoulders in apical one-third; its apex with one pair of preapical steps. Wing dark brown, with a few isolated hyaline and yellow spots, dimorphic: male with many larger, female with a few smaller spots. —Вершинний членник яйцеклада с перетяжкою, с тупоугольными выступами и одной парой превершинных уступов. У самца много мелких, у самки немного желтых точек.

3a

Wing with entire hyaline subapical crossband: cells r_{4+5} , m (and also dm) each with large hyaline spot, containing no brown streaks.

Крыло с цельной превершинной прозрачной перевязью, не включающей бурых штрихов.

4

3b

Wing either with isolated spots forming broken rows or at least cells r_{4+5} , m and dm each with hyaline spots, containing brown streaks.

Крыло либо с изолированными пятнами, образующими разорванные ряды, а если с прозрачной перевязью, то ячейки r_{4+5} , m и dm с прозрачными пятнами, включающими бурые штрихи.

6

4a

O. albipila Loew

Either frontal, posterior notopleural or apical scutellar seta (or all of them) white. Thorax and femora mostly black. Mesonotum with long brown vittae.

Фронтальна, задня нотоплеуральна або вершинна щиткова (или все эти щетинки) білі. Грудь і бедра бурі. Среднеспинка з довгими бурими волосами.

4b

Frontal, all notopleural and scutellar setae black. Thorax and femora mostly reddish yellow. Mesonotum with short brown vittae anteriorly.

Фронтальна, все нотоплеуральні і щиткові щетинки чорні. Грудь і бедра червоно-жовті. Среднеспинка з короткими бурими волосами в передній половині.

5

5b

O. dracunculina Richter

Anterior orbital seta black. Wing with mostly yellow spots in brown fields. Central and Western Asia, Eastern Europe.

Передняя орбитальная щетинка черная. Крыло преимущественно с желтыми пятнышками на буром поле. Центральная и Западная Азия, Восточная Европа.

5a

O. obesa Loew

Anterior orbital seta white. Wing with both hyaline and yellow spots in brown fields. Iberian Peninsula.

Передняя орбитальная щетинка белая. Крыло с прозрачными и желтыми пятнами на буром поле. Пиренейский полуостров.

6b

Parafacial microtrichose. Wing with round hyaline spots, narrowly isolated, with crossbands, broken into hyaline spots.

Скула ошпеленная. Крыло с округлыми, узко изолированными прозрачными пятнами, образующими разорванные перевязи.

7

6a

O. guttatofasciata Loew

Parafacial shining. Wing with subrectangular hyaline spots, widely touching and forming entire crossbands with brown spots inside.

Скула блестящая. Крыло с почти прямоугольными, широко соприкасающимися прозрачными пятнами, образующими непрерывные перевязи с бурыми полосками внутри них.

7b

Apical scutellar (a sctl) setae present.

Вершинные щитковые щетинки (a sctl) развиты.

8

7a

O. nebulosa Wiedemann

Apical scutellar (a sctl) setae lacking.

Вершинные щитковые щетинки (a sctl) отсутствуют.

8b

O. lutulenta Loew

Aculeus with long apical portion (distal to ventral lobes); its apex with one pair of preapical steps. Wing with small yellow dots, much narrower than dark fields between them in males and females. — Верхинний членик яйцеклада с длинной верхушкой и 1 парой уступов. Крыло с многочисленными желтыми точками, которые уже разделяющих их темных промежутков.

8a

O. parietina Linnaeus

Aculeus with short apical portion (distal to ventral lobes); its apex with two pairs of preapical steps. Wing with large yellow dots, in males, often touching to each other and wider than dark fields between them; female with somewhat smaller spots. — Верхинний членик яйцеклада с 2 парами уступов. Крыло с большими желтыми пятнами, у самцов соприкасающимися, у самок изолированными.

O. albipila (Loew, 1869)

Фронтальная, орбитальная, глазковая и обе нотоплевральные щетинки белые, одна пара щитковых щетинок. Крыло с 2 почти полными продольными перевязями. Среднеспинка серая, с 4 темно-бурыми продольными полосами. Вершинный членик яйцеклада короткий, с 2 парами предвершинных уступов.

Frontal, orbital, ocellar seta and both notopleural setae white; one pair of scutellar setae. Wing with two almost complete hyaline crossbands. Mesonotum silver grey with 4 dark brown vittae. Femora brown. Aculeus short, with two preapical steps.

O. dracunculina Richter, 1990

Фронтальная и обе нотоплевральные щетинки черные, передняя орбитальная щетинка черная, задняя — белая, 2 пары щитковых щетинок. Крыло с 2 полными прозрачными перевязями. Вершинный членик яйцевода не изучен.

Frontal seta and both notopleural setae black; anterior orbital seta black, posterior white; 2 pairs of scutellar setae. Wing with two complete hyaline crossbands. Aculeus not examined.

O. flavipennis (Loew, 1844)

Presutural dorsocentral seta present. Aculeus conspicuously constricted, with blunt shoulders in apical one-third; its apex with one pair of preapical steps. Wing dark brown, with a few isolated hyaline and yellow spots, dimorphic: male with many larger, female with a few smaller spots.

Предшовные досоцентральные щетинки развиты. Вершинный членик яйцеклада явственно сужен, с тупоугольными выступами в вершинной трети и парой преапикальных уступов. Крыло темно-бурое, с немногочисленными изолированными прозрачными и желтыми пятнами, диморфное: самец с более многочисленными и крупными пятнами, самка с немногими мелкими пятнами.

O. guttatofasciata (Loew, 1850)

Greyish-yellow microtrichose species with shining parafacials black frontal, anterior orbital, and anterior notopleural setae; 2 pairs of scutellar setae. Aculeus evenly narrowed, without steps.

Серовато-жовто опылений вид с блестящими скулами, черными фронтальной, передней орбитальной и нотолевральной щетинками; 2 пары щитковых щетинок. Основной членик яйцеклада постепенно сужающийся, без предвершинных уступов.

O. lutulenta (Loew, 1869)

Густо серовато-желто опыленный вид с черными фронтальной, передними орбитальной и нотоплевральной щетинками; 2 пары щитковых щетинок. Основной членик яйцевода с длинной и узкой вершинной частью, с одной парой предвершинных уступов.

Densely greyish-yellow microtrichose species with black frontal, anterior orbital, and anterior notopleural setae; 2 pairs of scutellar setae. Aculeus with very long and narrow apical portion, bearing one pair of preapical steps.

O. nebulosa (Wiedemann, 1817)

Одна пара щиткових щетинок. Вершинний членик яйцеклада с отчетливыми выступами в вершинной трети и с одной парой предвершинных уступов. Крыло темно-бурое, с изолированными прозрачными и желтоватыми пятнами.

One pair of scutellar setae. Aculeus with produced shoulders in apical one-third and one pair of preapical steps. Wing dark brown, with a few isolated hyaline and yellow spots.

O. obesa Loew, 1862

Фронтальная и обе нотоплевральные щетинки черные, обе орбитальные щетинки белые, 2 пары щитковых щетинок. Крыло с 2 почти полными прозрачными перевязями. Верхинный членик яйцеклада с двумя парами уступов.

Frontal seta and both notopleural setae black; both orbital setae white; 2 pairs of scutellar setae. Wing with two almost complete hyaline crossbands. Aculeus with 2 pairs of steps.

O. parietina (Linnaeus, 1758)

Anterior orbital black, posterior orbital and notopleural setae white, 2 pairs of scutellar setae. Wing with large isolated hyaline and yellow spots. Aculeus with 2 pairs of preapical steps.

Передня орбитальна чорна, задні орбитальна і нотоплевральна щетинки білі, 2 пари щиткових щетинок. Крыло з крупними ізолюваними прозорчаними і жовтими плямами. Вершинний членик яйцеклада з двома парами передвершинних уступов.

O. variabilis (Chen, 1938)

Предшовные дорсоцентральные щетинки развиты. Крыло с диффузным буровато-охристым рисунком. Вершинный членник яйцеклада равномерно заострен, без угловатых выступов или предевершинных уступов.

Presutural dorsocentral setae present. Wing with diffuse ochreous brown pattern. Aculeus evenly tapered, without shoulders or steps.

***Oxya albipila* Loew, 1869**

Loew, 1869: 17; Hendel, 1927: 165; Richter, 1965: 147; 1970: 167; Foote, 1984: 108; Korneyev, 1987: 87; 1990: 414; Norrbom et al., 1999: 179.

Material examined. Russia: Ulyanovsk Region: Main Distr., Podlesnoe, chalky steppe, 15.06.2005, 1 ♂ (Evstigneev); idem, 26.06.2005, 1 ♀, 1 ♂; Surskoe Distr., 8 km N of Boshoy Kuvay, forest edge, 8.07.1999, 1 ♂ (Isaev); Radischevo Distr., Srednikovo, Malaya Atmala, edge of mixed forest, transiting into chalky steppe, 14.07.2010, 1 ♀ (Evstigneev); Radischevo Distr., Vyazovka, saline steppe, 30.07–1.08.1994, 2 ♀ (Isaev & Isaeva); 6 km N of Vyazovka, saline steppe, 6.08.2004, 1 ♀ (Evstigneev). Samara Region: Bolshaya Chernigovka Distr., Verkhnie Rostashi, Verkhnie Skripali tract, saline steppe, gully bottom, 17.07.2009, 2 ♂ (Evstigneev). Astrakhan Region: Akhtuba Distr., S of Nizhniy Baskunchak, saline steppe on slopes and ravine with saline brook, falling into Baskunchak Lake, 10.05.2013, 1 ♂ (Evstigneev) (CDE).

Distribution. Sands in the basins of Dnipro, Volga, and Ural; saline steppes.

Biology. Larvae feed in the stems of *Artemisia marshalliana* Spreng. and *A. arenaria* DC. (Korneyev, 1987, 1990), inducing no galls.

Comments. *O. albipila* belongs in the *parietina* group of species with two steps on aculeus apex, which also includes *O. parietina* (Linnaeus), *O. amurensis* Hendel, *O. fusca* Chen, *O. albofasciata* Chen (Korneyev, 1990), and *O. obesa* Loew (Perez & Korneyev, 2013), and, with some reservations, *O. lutulenta* Loew and *O. tarbagatajensis* Korneyev, both having long apical portion of aculeus and only one pair of steps on it, and *O. dracunculina* V. Richter, for which female genitalia have not been studied. Inside this group, it shares more or less banded wing pattern (Fig. 6) with *O. albofasciata*, *O. obesa* and *O. dracunculina*, clearly differing from them by having numerous white setae, first of all, by the frontal and ocellar seta, and both orbital setae, and often also by anepisternal, katepisternal, anepimeral, and also by the apical scutellar seta either absent or rarely replaced by short white seta), in combination with black, silver microtrichose thorax and dark brown striate mesonotum.

***Oxya dracunculina* Richter, 1990**

dracunculi Richter, 1964: 288; 1965: 147; 1975: 596; Foote, 1984: 109 (*Oxya*), preoccupied name, non *Oxya dracunculi* Rondani, 1870 (synonym of *Campiglossa punctella* (Fällen, 1817)). — *dracunculina* Richter, 1990: 394 (new replacement name for *Oxya dracunculi* Richter, 1964); Korneyev, 1990: 414 (*Oxya*).

Material examined. Russia: Orenburg Region: Orenburg, 2.06.1986, 1 ♀ (Ermolenko) (SIZK).

Distribution. European Russia (South-East), Kazakhstan, Mongolia.

Biology. Unknown. Type specimens were swept from *Artemisia dracunculus* L., but have not been reared since then.

Comments. This species is very similar to a rare Iberian species *O. obesa* in the presence of two pairs of black notopleural and scutellar setae, differing mainly by having the anterior orbital seta black. The only available female has the postabdomen entirely destroyed by

dermestids, so genital differences could not be found. Their variability and differences require additional study.

***Oxya flavipennis* Loew, 1844**

flavescens Robineau-Desvoidy, 1830: 756 (*Oxya*). — *flavipennis* Loew, 1844: 368 (*Trypeta*), as a new replacement name for *Trypeta flavescens* Robineau-Desvoidy, 1830 (= *Oxya flavescens* Robineau-Desvoidy, 1830), non *Trypeta flavescens* (Fabricius, 1798), (= *Musca flavescens* Fabricius, 1798); 1846: 35; Schiner, 1858: 669 (*Trypeta*); Loew, 1862: 86; Becker, 1905: 133; Hendel, 1927: 165; Séguy, 1934: 148; Richter, 1965: 147; 1970: 161; Foote, 1984: 109; White, 1988: 48; Merz, 1994: 55; Norrbom et al., 1999: 179; Merz & Korneyev, 2004 (*Oxya*).

Material examined. Russia: Ulyanovsk Region: Main Distr., Podlesnoe, chalky steppe, 15.06.2005, 1 ♂ (Evstigneev); idem, 26.06.2005, 1 ♀, 1 ♂; Surskoe Distr., 8 km N of Boshoy Kuvay, forest edge, 8.07.1999, 1 ♂ (Isaev); Radischevo Distr., Srednikovo, Malaya Atmala, edge of mixed forest, transiting into chalky steppe, 14.07.2010, 1 ♀ (Evstigneev); Radischevo Distr., Vyazovka, saline steppe, 30.07–1.08.1994, 2 ♀ (Isaev & Isaeva); 6 km N of Vyazovka, saline steppe, 6.08.2004, 1 ♀ (Evstigneev). Samara Region: Bolshaya Chernigovka Distr., Verkhnie Rostashi, Verkhnie Skripali tract, saline steppe, gully bottom, 17.07.2009, 2 ♂ (Evstigneev) (CDE).

Distribution. Most of Europe (except North, Ireland and Portugal: see map); northern Kazakhstan; West Siberia; Turkey, Caucasus.

Biology. Larvae in galls on rhizome of *Achillea millefolium* L. (Kieffer, 1891; Houard, 1909).

Comments. This species can be easily differentiated from other species of *Oxya* based on combination of the presence of additional, presutural dorsocentral seta (also in *O. variabilis* Chen, 1938), with the darker and dimorphic wing pattern including a few larger and less confluent yellow dots (numerous larger and confluent yellow dots in *O. variabilis*) and the constricted aculeus with more or less conspicuous shoulders (evenly narrowed in *O. variabilis*).

***Oxya guttatofasciata* (Loew, 1850)**

Loew, 1850: 55 (*Trypeta*); Becker, 1905: 133; 1908: 288; Hendel, 1927: 166; Zia, 1937: 194; Zia & Chen, 1938: 102; Richter, 1965: 147; 1970: 161; 1975: 596; Korneyev, 1990: 416; Wang, 1998: 282; Norrbom et al., 1999: 179 (*Oxya*).

Distribution. Kazakhstan (North and East), Kyrgyzstan, Tajikistan, Asian Russia (Ural, Altai, South of Eastern Siberia, Far East), Mongolia, China (from Xingjian to Heilongjian).

Biology. This species is very common in the stands of *Artemisia dracunculus* L. in Kyrgyzstan, but no larvae have been found either in stems or galls (V. Korneyev personal observation).

Comments. We were unable to trace any material to confirm the presence of this species in Southern Ural (Korneyev, 1990); the species is included in the key, as it is rather probable to be found in the south-eastern regions of European Russia.

***Oxya lutulenta* Loew, 1869**

Loew, 1869: 55; Becker, 1905: 133; Hendel, 1927: 167; Richter, 1965: 147; 1970: 162; 1975: 595 (dubious record); Korneyev, 1990: 414; Norrbom et al., 1999: 179 (*Oxya*).

Material examined. Russia: Ulyanovsk Region: Radischevo Distr., Vyazovka, steppe, 23–24.05.1994, 2 ♀ (Isaeva); idem, 4 km S of Vyazovka, saline steppe, 7–10.05.2000, 2 ♀, 1 ♂ (Isaeva); idem, 5 km N of Vyazovka, saline steppe, 30.04–4.05.2001, 4 ♂, 2 ♀ (1 ♀ dissected) (Isaev & Isaeva) (CDE; SIZK); idem, 8 km S of Vyazovka, edge of a gully wood in saline steppe, 10.05.2001, 1 ♀ (Isaev); idem, 6 km S of Vyazovka, saline steppe, 2–11.05.2001, 2 ♂ (Isaev & Isaeva); idem, 6 km S of Vyazovka, saline steppe, 6–7.05.2001, 3 ♀, 1 ♂ (Evstigneev); idem, 8 km S of Vyazovka, edge of a gully wood in saline steppe, 4.05.2002, 1 ♀ (A. Kovalev); Sengileevo Distr., Shilovka, chalky steppe, 22.06.2002, forest edge, 1 ♀ (Isaeva). Samara Region: Pestrava Distr., Mayskoe, saline steppe, 22.05.2009, 1 ♀ (Evstigneev); idem, 9.05.2010, 1 ♂ (Evstigneev); Pestrava Distr., Sadovka, disturbed saline steppe, 8.05.2010, 1 ♂ (Evstigneev); Bolshaya Chernigovka Distr., Verkhnie Rostashi, Verkhnie Skripali tract, saline steppe, 19.05.2007, 2 ♂, 4 ♀ (Evstigneev) (CDE).

Distribution. Russia (steppes eastern of Volga); Kazakhstan; record from Mongolia (Richter, 1975) based on a single male, cannot be either confirmed or disproved.

Biology. Host plants unknown. All the records are from late spring or early summer.

Comments. This species shares such characters as spotted wing pattern, one pair of dorsocentral and two pairs of scutellar setae with many other species of *Oxyina* reliably differing by the shape of aculeus with very long and narrow apical portion, bearing one pair of preapical steps.

Oxyina nebulosa (Wiedemann, 1817)

Wiedemann, 1817: 76 (*Tephritis*); Hendel, 1927: 167; Séguy, 1934: 148; Richter, 1970: 161; Foote, 1984: 109; White, 1988: 48; Freidberg & Kugler, 1989: 106; Merz, 1994: 55; Norrbom et al., 1999: 179; Hajjighorbani, Goldasteh & Mohamadzade Namin, 2012: 27 (*Oxyina*). — *femoralis* Robineau-Desvoidy 1830: 756 (*Oxyina*). — *nigrofemorata* Meigen, 1838: 355 (*Trypeta*) (new replacement name for *Oxyina femoralis* Robineau-Desvoidy, 1830). — *proboscidea* Loew, 1844: 371 (*Trypeta*); Schiner, 1864: 154 (*Tephritis*); Loew, 1862: 87 (*Oxyina*). — *proboscidae*: Becker, 1905: 134 (*Oxyina*) (misspelling). — *cribrina* Rondani, 1870: 128 (*Oxyina*). — *corticina* Rondani, 1870: 127 (*Oxyina*).

Material examined. Russia: Ulyanovsk Region: Radischevo Distr., Vyazovka, steppe, 23.05.1994, 1 ♂ (Isaeva); idem, saline steppe, 25.05.1994, 1 ♀ (Isaeva); idem, 6 km N of Vyazovka, 18.08.2001, saline steppe, 1 ♂ (Evstigneev); Inza Distr., Yulovo, 20.07.1996, 1 ♂ (collector not given) (CDE).

Distribution. Portugal and Great Britain to East of European Russia and North-West of Iran and from South of Norway and Finland to Sicily and Israel.

Biology. Larvae in rhizome galls on *Achillea fragrantissima* (Freidberg & Kugler, 1989), *Achillea* sp. (Hajjighorbani, Goldasteh & Mohamadzade Namin, 2012) in the Middle East and *Leucanthemum vulgare* and *Tanacetum corymbosum* (Houard, 1909) in Europe, but comprehensive studies on its biology were not conducted. Number of generations per year is unknown.

Comments. *O. nebulosa* differs from other species of the genus based on the combination of only one pair of scutellar setae and the aculeus with well-defined shoulders and its apex with one preapical step.

Oxyina obesa Loew, 1862

Loew, 1862: 87; Becker, 1905: 134; Hendel, 1927: 168; Foote, 1984: 110; Norrbom et al., 1999: 180; Korneyev & Perez Hidalgo, 2013: 24 (*Oxyina*).

Material examined. Holotype ♀: Spain: “Andalus// 24/5 Stgd.” [Staudinger], “coll. H. Loew”, “obe-// sa// Loew” (ZMHB). Non-type: Spain: Province of León: San Juan de Paluezas, reared from shoots of *Artemisia campestris glutinosa* with galls, coll. 26.02.2010 — exit 16.03.2011 (Perez Hidalgo leg.) (SIZK).

Distribution. Spain.

Biology. One female was reared from *Artemisia campestris glutinosa*, from shoots with the bud galls that remind those of *Oedaspis* or *Hendrella*. As *O. albipila* and *O. parietina*, the species related to *O. obesa*, induce no galls, it is quite possible that the single fly could emerge from a twig chamber rather than from a gall. Further observations on the localisation of larvae are needed.

Comments. *O. obesa* was redescribed in detail by Hendel (1927), and we do not repeat its description here. VAK studied the holotype female in 1999, and prepared the illustrations used in this paper. The wing pattern in the holotype has the wing hyaline crossbands including a few dark spots, whereas in the specimen from León they are almost purely hyaline and unbroken; both specimens share the anterior orbital seta white (black in the other species of *Oxyina*, except *O. albipila*) combined with the frontal seta black (white in *O. albipila*, but black in the other species of *Oxyina*), and posterior notopleural seta black (also in *O. dracunculina*), its diagnostic combination of characters. The wing pattern and shape of aculeus are similar to those in *O. albipila*, but latter species differ by having numerous white setae instead of black (see above). *O. obesa* looks very similar to *O. dracunculina*, especially in the wing pattern and reddish body coloration and black posterior notopleural seta; unfortunately, no females of *O. dracunculina* have been dissected to study the shape of aculeus, and the variability of both species known from a few specimens only is not studied.

Oxyina parietina (Linnaeus, 1758)

Linnaeus, 1758: 599; Fabricius, 1782: 450; 1794: 350 (*Musca*); 1805: 319 (*Tephritis*); Meigen, 1826: 334; Loew, 1844: 366 (*Trypeta*); 1862: 85; Becker, 1905: 134; Hendel, 1927: 168; Séguy, 1934: 148; Richter, 1970: 162; Foote, 1984: 110; White, 1988: 48; Korneyev, 1990: 407; Merz, 1994: 55; Norrbom et al., 1999: 180 (*Oxyina*). — *cinerea* Robineau-Desvoidy, 1830: 755 (*Oxyina*). — *pantherina* Fallén, 1820: 10 (*Tephritis*). — *nasuta* Hering, 1936: 60; Foote, 1984: 109; Norrbom et al., 1999: 179 (*Oxyina*), possible synonymy.

Material examined. Russia: Ulyanovsk Region: Main Distr., Podlesnoe, chalky steppe, 06.06.2010, 1 ♀ (Evstigneev) (CDE).

Distribution. France to northern Kazakhstan and southern Sweden and Finland to Bulgaria.

Biology. Larvae of *O. parietina* short drop-like, living in chambers inside young stems of *Artemisia vulgaris* L., a widespread weed; the larvae induce no visible galls (Volkov & Volkova, 1988). Adults are active from the end of April to beginning of June. One generation per year.

Comments. *O. parietina* occurs in the regions of western Palaearctics with moderate climate. Records from eastern Palaearctics obviously belong to *O. amurensis* Hendel, 1927 and *O. stackelbergi* Korneyev, 1990 (Korneyev, 1990). *O. parietina* was considered to be a potential agent of biocontrol of *A. vulgaris* in Canada and USA (Groppe, 1990; Barney J. N. & DiTommaso, 2003), but has not been introduced to North America yet. *O. nasuta* was described based on a specimen from Ukraine, but the characters proposed by Hering (1936) are variable in the genus and cannot be used for reliable differentiation of species. We leave its formal synonymization pending until additional material from its type locality is collected.

Oxya variabilis Chen, 1938 (Figs. 2, 4–10, 27–36)

Zia & Chen, 1938: 97; Foote, 1984: 94; 1990: 420; Norrbom et al., 1999: 180. — *notabilis* Chen: Zia & Chen, 1938: 86 (*Sinoxyna*); Foote, 1984: 123; Korneyev, 1990: 420; Norrbom et al., 1999: 180. — *gilva* Dirlbek & Dirlbek, 1971: 16; Dirlbeková, 1982: 42 (*Grandoxyna*); Foote, 1984: 123; Korneyev, 1990: 420; Norrbom et al., 1999: 180.

Material examined. Russia: Ulyanovsk Region: Radischevo Distr., Vyazovka, saline land, 23.09.1995, 1 ♀ (dissected) (Isaev) (SIZK). Samara Region: Pestrava Distr., Mayskoe, saline steppe, lowland, southernwood stands, swept from *Artemisia abrotanum* L., 13.08.2000, 2 ♂, 1 ♀, 2 specimens without abdomen (Evstigneev) (SIZK; CDE); idem, saline steppe, lowland, 11.08.2002, 1 ♂ (Evstigneev) (SIZK); idem, saline steppe, lowland, southernwood stands, swept from *Artemisia abrotanum* L., 19.08.2011, 1 ♀ (Evstigneev); idem, saline land near water, swept from *Artemisia abrotanum* L., 20.08.2011, 1 ♀, 1 ♂ (Evstigneev) (CDE).

Distribution. Mongolia, China, East Siberia (Chita Region) and Far East Russia (Amur Region) (Korneyev, 1990). This is the first record from European Russia and Europe as a whole.

Biology. Dirlbeková (1982) reported *Artemisia macrocephala* Jacquem. as a host plant of *Grandoxyna gilva*, but without any information on localization in the host plant or inducing galls. Another probable host plant is *Artemisia abrotanum* L., but the flies were only swept in the stands.

Comments. This species shares the presence of additional (presutural) dorsocentral seta with *O. flavipennis*, differing by more diffuse wing pattern, similar in male and female, and by the aculeus evenly pointed without any shoulders and steps. Other species having no steps or shoulders on aculei (*O. longicauda* V. Korneyev and *O. tianshanica* V. Korneyev) differ by the absence of presutural dorsocentral seta and more contrasting wing patterns.

Discussion

The genus *Oxya* occurs throughout Eurasia, with the highest species richness in the steppes of Central Asia, where their host plants of the tribe Anthemideae (*Artemisia*, *Achillea*, *Leucanthemum* and possibly other) are the most abundant and rich of species. Series of specimens reared from host plants are rare in collections, and the wing pattern variability ranges remain poorly understood, making identification of some species very difficult.

Revision of the Chinese species, which would involve more reared material, is still of need, as some nominal species are poorly defined (Korneyev, 1990). The faunas of South-Eastern Kazakhstan, Kyrgyzstan, Tajikistan, Turkmenistan, Uzbekistan and Afghanistan remain almost untreated, with 5–9 species recognized in collections. *Oxya* larvae are believed to be either gall-inducers on the underground buds on rhizome, or inhabitants of shoots on semi-shrubs of *Artemisia*.

Acknowledgements

The authors thank S. B. Glagolev and K. A. Grebennikov, Bogdinsko-Baskunchaksky Nature Reserve for the permission to collect material used in this paper. VAK thanks Joachim Ziegler (ZMHB) for the opportunity to study the material mentioned in this paper. Nicolás Perez Hidalgo (University of León) kindly borrowed or gifted specimens they collected to VAK.

References

- Becker, T. (1905) Cyclorrhapha Schizophora: Holometopa. In: T. Becker, M. Bezzi, K. Kertész und P. Stein. *Katalog der paläarktischen Dipteren. Band IV*, Budapest, 1–273.
- Becker, T. (1908) Zur Kenntnis der Dipteren von Central-Asien. I. Cyclorrhapha schizophora holometopa und Orthorrhapha brachycera. *Ezhagodnik Zoodicheskogo Muzeya Rossiyskoy Akademii Nauk*, (1907), 12, 253–317.
- Barney, J. N. & DiTommaso, A. (2003). The biology of Canadian weeds. 118. *Artemisia vulgaris* L. *Canadian Journal of Plant Sciences*, **83**, 205–215.
- Dirlbek, J. & Dirlbek, K. (1971) Ergebnisse der mongolisch-tschechoslowakischen entomologische-botanischen Expeditionen (1965, 1966) in die Mongolei. (Nr. 23: Trypetidae). *Acta Faunistica Entomologica Musei Nationalis Pragae* **14**(156), 9–18.
- Dirlbeková, O. (1982) Wirtspflanzen einiger Fruchtfliegenarten (Diptera, Tephritidae) in der Mongolei, 6th meeting of Czechoslovak dipterists, Cikhaj near Zdar N.S., Oct. 22–24, 1980. *Folia Facultatis Scientiarum Naturalium Universitatis Purkynianae Brunensis*, **23**, 41–44.
- Fabricius, J. C. (1782) *Species insectorum exhibentes eorum differentias specificas, synonyma, avctorum loca natalia, metamorphosin adiectis observationibus, descriptionibus. Tome II*. C.E. Bohnii, Hambvrgi et Kilonii (1781), 1–517.
- Fabricius, J. C. (1794) *Entomologia systematica emendata et aucta. Secundum classes, ordines, genera, species, adiectis synonymis, locis, observationibus, descriptionibus. Tome 4*. C. G. Proft, Hafniae, [1–6] + 1–472 + [1–5].
- Fabricius, J. C. (1805) *Systema antliatorum secundum ordines, genera, species, adiectis synonymis, locis, observationibus, descriptionibus*. Reichard, Brunsvigae, 1 + 1–373 + 1–30.
- Fällen, C. F. (1820) *Part I. In: Ortalides sveciae*. Berling, Lundae, 1–34.
- Foote, R. H. (1984) Family Tephritidae (Trypetidae). In: Soós, Á. & Papp, L. eds. *Catalogue of Palaearctic Diptera. Vol. 9. Micropezidae — Agromyzidae*. Akadémiai Kiadó & Backhuis, Budapest & Amsterdam, 66–149.
- Freidberg, A. & Kugler, J. (1989) *Fauna Palaestina. Insecta 04. Diptera: Tephritidae*. Israel Academy of Sciences & Humanities, Jerusalem, [i–vi] + 1–212, 1–VIII + 1 map.

- Groppe, V. K. (1990). Biology, ecology and parasitoids of *Oxyna parietina* L. (Dipt., Tephritidae), a possible candidate for the biological control of *Artemisia vulgaris* L. *Journal of Applied Entomology*, **110**, 438–448.
- Hajighorbani, S., Goldasteh, Sh., Mohamadzade Namin, S. (2012) Fruit flies (Diptera: Tephritidae) of Markazi Province (Iran), with a new record for Iranian Fauna. *Ukrainska Entomofaunistyka*, **3**(3), 25–29.
- Hendel, F. (1927) 49. Trypetidae. In: Lindner, E. ed. *Die Fliegen der palaearktischen Region*, E. Schweizerbart, Stuttgart, 5(16–19), 1–221 + I–XVII.
- Hering, E. M. (1936) Zur Systematik und Biologie palaearktischer Bohrfliiegen. 10. Beitrag zur Kenntnis der Trypetidae (Dipt.). *Konowia*, **15**, 54–64.
- Houard, C. (1909) *Les zoocécidies des plantes d'Europe et du Bassin de la Méditerranée. Tome II*. A. Hermann et Fils, Paris, i-xvi + 571–1247 + 1 pl.
- Kieffer, J.-J. (1891) Die Zoocécidien Lothringens (Fortsetzung). *Entomologische Nachrichten*, **17**, 220–224, 230–240, 252–256.
- Korneyev V. A. (1987) Little known species of Tephritidae (Diptera) of the Ukrainian fauna. In: Savchenko E. N., ed. *Fauna and biocoenotic associations of insects in Ukraine*. Naukova dumka, Kiev, 83–87. [In Russian]
- Korneyev, V. A. (1990) A review of *Sphenella* and *Paroxyna* series of genera (Diptera, Tephritidae, Tephritinae) of eastern Palaearctic. *Nasekomye Mongolii*, **11**, 395–470.
- Korneyev, V. A. (2004) *Flies of the tephritoid complex (Diptera, Platystomatidae, Pyrgotidae, Tephritidae) of the Palaearctic Region (phylogeny, systematics, trophic connections, distribution). Theses for the Doctor of Biological Sciences degree. I. I. Schmalhausen Institute of Zoology, National Academy of Sciences of Ukraine*, 1–789. (Manuscript, in Ukrainian; available at <http://www.archive.org/details/FliesOfTheTephritoidComplexDipteraPlatystomatidaePyrgotidae>)
- Korneyev, V. A. & Ovchinnikova, O. G. (2004) Tephritidae. In: Lehr, P. A., ed. *Key to the Insects of Russian Far East. Vol. VI. Diptera and Siphonaptera, Pt. 3*, Dal'nauka, Vladivostok, 456–564.
- Korneyev, V. A. & Perez Hidalgo, N. (2013) Rediscovery of *Oxyna obesa* Loew (Diptera: Tephritidae) in Spain. *Ukrainska Entomofaunistyka*, **4**(1), 24.
- Linnaeus, C. (1758) *Systema naturae per regna tria naturae, secundum classes, ordines, genera, species, cum characteribus, differentiis, synonymis, locis. Tomus I. Editio decima, reformata*. L. Salvii, Holmiae, 1–824.
- Loew, H. (1844) Kritische Untersuchung der europäischen Arten des Genus *Trypeta* Meig. *Zeitschrift für Entomologie (Germar)*, **5**, 312–437.
- Loew, H. (1846) Fragmente zur Kenntniss der europäischen Arten einiger Dipterengattungen. *Linnaea Entomologica*, **1**, 319–530.
- Loew, H. (1850) Sechs neue Arten der Gattung *Trypeta*. *Stettiner Entomologische Zeitung*, **11**, 52–59.
- Loew, H. (1862) *Die europäischen Bohrfliiegen (Trypetidae)*. W. Junk, Wien, 1–128.
- Loew, H. (1869) Revision der europäischen Trypetina. *Zeitschrift für die Gesamten Naturwissenschaften*, **34**(7/8), 1–24.
- Meigen, J. W. (1826) *Systematische Beschreibung der bekannten europäischen zweiflügeligen Insekten. Fünfter Theil*. Schulz, Hamm, i–xii + 1–412.
- Meigen, J. W. (1838) *Systematische Beschreibung der bekannten europäischen zweiflügeligen Insekten. Siebenter Theil oder Supplementband*. Schulz, Hamm, i–xii + 1–434 + [1].
- Merz, B. (1994) Diptera: Tephritidae. *Insecta Helvetica — Fauna*, HEG, Genève, 10, 1–198.
- Merz, B. & Korneyev, V. A. (2004). Fauna Europaea: Tephritidae. In: Pape T., ed. *Fauna Europaea: Diptera Cyclorhapha*. Fauna Europaea, version 1.1, <http://www.faunaeur.org>. Accessed 17.06.2013.
- Norrbom, A. L., Carroll, L. E., Thompson, F. C., White I. M., & Freidberg, A. (1999) Systematic Database of Names, In: Thompson F. C., ed. *Fruit Fly Expert Identification System and Systematic Information Database, Myia*, (1998), 9, 65–299.
- Richter, V. A. (1964) [New species of flies (Diptera) in Kazakhstan]. *Trudy Zoologicheskogo Instituta, Leningrad*, **34**, 286–290 [In Russian]
- Richter, V. A. (1965) A review of the fauna of fruit-flies (Diptera, Trypetidae) of Kazakhstan. *Entomologicheskoe Obozrenie*, **44**, 141–150 [In Russian].
- Richter, V. A. (1970) Sem. Tephritidae (Trypetidae) — pestrokyrlyki. In: Bei-Bienko, G. Y., ed. *Opredelitel nasekomykh evropeyskoy chasti SSSR. Tom 5. Diptera, Siphonaptera. Ch. 2. [Keys to the USSR fauna published by ZIN AN SSSR, 103]*. Nauka, Leningrad, 132–172 [In Russian].
- Richter, V. A. (1975) On the fauna of fruit-flies (Diptera, Tephritidae) of the Mongolian People's Republic. *Nasekomye Mongolii*, **3**, 582–602 [In Russian].
- Richter, V. A. (1990) A new name for *Oxyna dracunculi* Richter (Diptera, Tephritidae). *Nasekomye Mongolii*, **11**, 394 [In Russian].
- Robineau-Desvoidy, J. B. (1830) Essai sur les Myodaires. *Mémoires présentés par divers savants, Academie Royale des Sciences, Institut de France, Classe des Sciences Mathématiques et Physique*, **2**, 1–813.
- Rondani, C. (1870) Ortalidinae Italicae collectae, distinctae et in ordinum dispositae. Dipterologiae Italicae prodromus. Pars VII. Fasc. 4 (sect. 1) [concl.]. *Bullettino della Societa Entomologica Italiana*, **2**, 105–133.
- Schiner, I. R. (1858) Diptera austriaca. Aufzählung aller im Kaiserthume Oesterreich bisher aufgefundenen Zweiflügler. IV. Die österreichischen Trypeten. *Verhandlungen der Zoologisch-Botanischen Gesellschaft in Wien*, **8**, 635–700.
- Schiner, I. R. (1864) *Fauna austriaca. Die Fliegen (Diptera). Nach der analytischen Methode bearbeitet, mit der Charakteristik sämtlicher europäischer Gattungen, der Beschreibung aller in Deutschland vorkommenden Arten und der Aufzählung aller bisher beschriebenen europäischen Arten. Vol. 2*. Wien, I–XXXII + 1–658
- Séguy, E. (1934) Diptères (Brachycères) (Muscidae Acalypterae et Scatophagidae). *Faune de France*, **28**, I–IV + 1–832.
- Wang, X.-j. (1998) The fruit flies (Diptera: Tephritidae) of the East Asian Region. *Acta Zootaxonomica Sinica* (1996), **21**(Supplement), 1–338 + [1–40] + I–XLI.
- White, I. M. (1988) Tephritid flies (Diptera: Tephritidae). *Handbooks for Identification of British Insects*, **10**(5a): 1–134.
- Wiedemann, C. R. W. (1817) Neue Zweiflügler (Diptera Linn.) aus der Gegend um Kiel. *Zoological Magazine (Wiedemann's)*, **1**(1), 61–86.
- Zia, Y. (1937) Study on the Trypetidae or fruit-flies of China. *Sinensia*, **8**, 103–226.
- Zia, Y. & Chen, S. H. (1938) Trypetidae of North China. *Sinensia*, **9**(1–2), 1–180.